

TEACHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES

Sotkulova Dildora Odinabekovna

teacher of the Language department.

The Academy of the Armed Forces of Republic of Uzbekistan

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Annotation. Foreign Language Teachers for Specific Purposes have a lot in common with teachers of general foreign language. The article discusses the factors that should be taken into account when teaching English for specific purposes. The author also provides a brief history of the creation of ESP.

Key words: English for specific purposes, needs analysis, professional environment, authentic material, authentic language.

There are many similarities between general foreign language teachers and foreign language teachers for specific purposes. For both it is necessary to consider linguistic development and teaching theories, to have insights in contemporary ideas regarding their own position and role as well as the position and role of foreign language learners in education and to face new technologies offered as an aid to improve their methodology. The most important difference lies in the learners and their purposes for learning English. At the present time the methodology of teaching English for specific purposes (ESP) is very relevant. Knowledge of English is a necessary requirement for hiring, for promotion, for communication with foreign colleagues. ESP students are usually adults who already have some acquaintance with English and are learning the language in order to communicate a set of professional skills and to perform particular job-related functions. At the same time, we should confess that the level of English (especially ESP) among university graduates is below than is expected. The approach to solving problems of teaching ESP varies over time and depends on many reasons. There was a belief in the 1960s that the primary purpose of ESP was to familiarize students with the technical terminology that was specific to this field of study, meaning that it was relevant to their eventual area of specialization. Typically, they would teach a foreign language's broad curriculum while enhancing it with relevant specialized terminology. Subsequently, educators specialising in English for post-secondary education (ESP) started to recognise the importance of semi-technical vocabulary (as defined by Kennedy and Bolito [3, 12]), which comprises phrases and expressions used in a scientific and technical setting. The instruction started to center on the objectives of the students at that same moment. The foundation of the ESP training program is the study of future specialists' demands.

So, the main aspects for developing a training program for students.

1. Special vocabulary. Even while future experts will find the scientific and technical vocabulary essential to grasp the book on the specialty beneficial, they typically show little interest in it when we introduce it to them. They find it to be a dull and pointless profession.

2. Authentic material, authentic language. When working with students, we frequently use content from specialty textbooks, texts about professions written especially for students studying this profession. Students are typically not interested in this either. However, reading authentic material related to a future profession is not the same as being able to read and write about a profession. Students in higher education attend lectures in their field of study, participate in problem-solving sessions in specialized writing classes, complete course projects and assignments, and pass industrial and field practice. They need authentic information, conference materials, operating instructions, and advertising brochures for various equipment used in their field of activity – not artificially created texts about their future profession. Students exhibit significantly more interest when we provide them with articles from international journals that they can use for their academic work, the thesis. Additionally, students can already be taught to deconstruct complex grammatical constructions and extract information from what they read by using such authentic material.

3. Needs analysis. It is important to understand that, before you teach students in a particular specialty, you must first conduct an analysis of their needs. Talking with special subject teachers will help you determine which skills students particularly need, such as reading, writing, and comprehending spoken language through auditory texts. Speaking and listening comprehension are crucial abilities because our academy's experts frequently participate in international conferences on professional subjects; they also send their research articles to foreign journals, do international internships, and send exchange students to study abroad. For this reason, it is crucial to design classes in a way that gives professional speaking and listening the space they deserve [1, 59].

4. Considering the specifics of this particular professional group. It is particularly crucial to train the skills required to attend conferences on professional subjects when working with experts and graduate students. When conducting conferences and presentations in a variety of professional fields, there are several factors to consider.

5. An additional consideration when creating an educational program for ESP learners, in our opinion, has to do with the material's author. ESP teachers typically use pre-made materials without making any modifications. This may lead to a number of issues, such as learners losing interest and material shortcomings. It is preferable for ESP teachers to prepare their own materials, particularly audio and video, in order to overcome such situations. Because the materials were created with their interests and language proficiency in mind, among other considerations, this may pique the interest of the ESP learners in the subject matter.

Teaching students how to write business letters is crucial when working with them in economics specializations. You cannot rely solely on the examples provided in business English textbooks in this situation [2, 79]. The following should be taught to students: structure, lack of punctuation in the introduction and conclusion, and the use of tying words and phrases (but, additionally, moreover) are all characteristics of contemporary business writing. ESP teachers ought to use real, authentic letters, faxes, e-mails, etc. as examples when instructing students on how to write business letters in English. It is imperative to consider that a considerable number of companies opt for a distinct correspondence style. As experts in the field of teaching English, it is our responsibility to teach students precisely the language that we constantly observe being used in authentic professional settings. It is critical that we are able to evaluate the circumstances. We must always be prepared to make improvements to our training program and teach students the real language of a variety of professional fields. To do this, we must carefully analyze our students' needs and apply the proper materials and methodologies. The majority of the language content that our students require is not included in any textbook, and this is something we must acknowledge.

Therefore, we must create and update our own methodological aids, which would include the necessary materials. What then is ESP? It involves teaching English with a focus on the essential requirements of students who will encounter real-world issues in their future endeavors. It takes a lot of time, effort, and—most importantly—competence in a variety of professional domains to teach ESP, which is an extremely challenging task. Additionally, ESP instructors need to be well-versed in the idiosyncrasies of the fields in which their students are specialized. This factor necessitates not only their superior English language skills but also their familiarity with industry-specific jargon. which would include the necessary materials. What then is ESP? It involves

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